

Practice Oriented Science: UAE – RUSSIA – INDIA

Proceedings of International University Scientific Forum
Date: 06 May, 2022

UAE, 2022

Proceedings of International
University Scientific Forum

Practice Oriented Science:
UAE – RUSSIA – INDIA

May 6, 2022

UAE, 2022

Proceedings of the International University Scientific
Forum **“Practice Oriented Science: UAE – RUSSIA
– INDIA”** (May 6, 2022, UAE), Part 1.

ISBN 978-5-905695-91-4

These Forum Proceedings combine materials of the conference – research papers and thesis reports of scientific workers. They examines technical and sociological issues of research issues. Some articles deal with theoretical and methodological approaches and principles of research questions of personality professionalization.

Authors are responsible for the accuracy of cited publications, facts, figures, quotations, statistics, proper names and other information.

ISBN 978-5-905695-91-4

©Scientific publishing house Infinity, 2022
©Group of authors, 2022

CONTENT

ECONOMICS

Investment risks and security threats <i>Mikhail Chernyakov, Akberov Kamal, Ivan Shuraev</i>	8
Variants of macroeconomics development after being affected by internal and external forces <i>Pil Eduard Anatolyevich</i>	13
Innovations and assessment of cooperation areas between Russia, India and the countries of the Arabian Peninsula (UAE, Saudi Arabia) based on the Gross Domestic Product structure (GDP) and the structure of the patents in force in these countries <i>Zhigalov Vladimir Ivanovich, Sokolova Mariia Vladimirovna</i>	26
Chinese 5G Technology market, M&A market and future development <i>Konev Dmitry Mikhailovich, Kharlanov Alexey Sergeevitch, Boboshko Andrey Alexandrovich</i>	36
Problems of digitalization and ways to solve them in the industry context <i>Larin Sergey Nikolaevich, Sokolov Nikolay Aleksandrovich, Lazareva Larisa Yuryevna</i>	45
The dynamic aspect of the development of managerial and professional competencies of the personnel of industrial enterprises <i>Larin Sergey Nikolaevich, Stebenyaeva Tatyana Viktorovna</i>	53
Risk Governance Structure and Firm Level Competitiveness: An Evidence from Select Sample in India <i>M. V. Shivaani, P. K. Jain, Surendra S. Yadav</i>	58

JURISPRUDENCE

Legal regulation of the use of distance learning technologies: stages, problems, prospects <i>Gaidareva Inna Nikolaevna, Shadzhe Leyla Azamatovna, Abregov Amir Ramazanovich</i>	65
---	----

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

Stages of development of bilingualism of Russian Germans in the situation of the foreign language environment <i>Baykova Olga Vladimirovna</i>	72
Poster-Busting as an relevant format of political communication in Russia <i>Rebrina Larisa Nikolaevna, Terentieva Elena Vitalievna</i>	78

**THE DYNAMIC ASPECT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF
MANAGERIAL AND PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF THE
PERSONNEL OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES**

Larin Sergey Nikolaevich

*Candidate of Technical Sciences, Lead Research Officer
Central Economics and Mathematics Institute, RAS*

Stebenyaeva Tatyana Viktorovna

*Candidate of Technical Sciences, Lead Specialist
Institute of International Accounting and Management Standards
Moscow*

Abstract. *The relevance of the study is determined by the need to study the factors of growth and development of the intellectual potential of enterprises, taking into account the changing conditions of their activities. The subject of the study is the dynamic aspect of the development of managerial and professional competencies of the personnel of enterprises, determined by the results of development activities. As a result of the study, statistically significant differences were revealed between the level of competencies before and after the training, as well as the relationship between the level of development of competencies and types of motivation of the personnel of enterprises.*

Keywords: *intellectual potential, personnel of enterprises, managerial and professional competencies, assessment center, dynamic aspect, types of motivation.*

Introduction

One of the key factors that ensure the successful operation of most modern enterprises is the increase in intellectual potential, taking into account the dynamics of development of managerial and professional competencies of their personnel. The need to form the intellectual potential of enterprises and its compliance with the required level is determined by the growing influence of the challenges of globalization and the intensification of market competition. To reduce this impact on the activities of enterprises, it is advisable to conduct training and development (learning and development) of the personnel of enterprises in order to improve their managerial and professional competencies. The subject of our research is the development of managerial and professional competencies of middle and top

managers of one of the enterprises in the construction industry.

Organization of the study

The study was carried out in two stages with an interval of one year. During this period, the management of the enterprise and employees of the HR department, within the framework of the advanced training system, carried out activities aimed at the growth and development of managerial and professional competencies of managers. The activities included group trainings, individual task-consultations, study of the recommended literature and its discussion. The sample of the study at the first stage included top (6 people) and middle (9 people) managers of one of the enterprises in the construction industry (heads of sales and production departments, heads of departments in different cities of the region). At the second stage, 8 people from the first sample participated in the study. All of them were trained within the system of professional development.

Materials and methods of research

The Assessment Center was chosen as the main method of conducting the study. During the study, the following tools were used: two independent business cases with a role-playing game; independent writing exercise; two team exercises; group discussion; mini interview. At the first stage of the study, in order to identify the types of motivation of the respondents, an additional test was conducted by V.I. Gerchikov by types of motivation [1]. When processing the obtained data, methods of qualitative and quantitative analysis were used. Statistical processing of data on the dynamics of competencies was carried out using the Kruskal-Wallis test using the SPSS 19 statistical package. The Mann-Whitney test was used to compare differences between groups of respondents with high and low scores by types of motivation.

Results and discussion

The main results of the study and the necessary explanations for them are presented below.

1. The introduction of systems for advanced training and retraining of personnel at enterprises opens up opportunities for implementing the dynamic aspect of the development of managerial and professional competencies of personnel.

In the course of the empirical study, measurements were taken at intervals of one year for the same group of respondents-managers who completed training within the framework of professional development systems during this period. As a result of the analysis and comparison of the data obtained, a dynamic aspect of the development of managerial and professional competencies of personnel was revealed and statistically significant differences were established. For data processing, the Kruskal-Wallis criterion was applied. It made it possible to measure the significance of changes in competencies between representatives of the same group over different time periods. In our case, we checked the effect of the training

[1]. The data presented in Table 1 indicate that there are statistically significant differences between the level of competences *Focus on results* and *Willingness to give feedback* (asymptotic significance of 0.046 and 0.038, respectively; highlighted in bold).

Table 1.
Changes in competencies as a result of training

Clusters	Competencies (measured 1 year apart)	Asymptotic significance
Personal effectiveness	Efficient use of time	0.059
	Focus on results	0.046
	Ability to prioritize and prioritize tasks	0.102
Decision making	Ability to predict activity	0.102
	Ability to make a to-do list	0.317
	Ability to gather information to make a decision	0.564
	Decision making ability	0.083
Goal setting	Ability to clearly assign tasks to subordinates	0.317
	Ability to ensure that subordinates understand the task	0.564
Control and correction	Ability to exercise control	0.084
	Ability to correct	0.180
Coordination	Ability to coordinate actions	0.317
Motivation	Ability to motivate and inspire	0.493
Development orientation	Willingness to give feedback	0.038
	Orientation to the development of oneself and others	0.084
Teamwork	Teamwork	0.157

Source: compiled by the authors.

Competence *Focus on results* is included in the *Personal efficiency* cluster and includes the following indicator indicators: the ability to set ambitious goals; clear presentation of the final result; willingness to take responsibility for the result and implement the decisions made.

The competence *Willingness to give feedback* is included in the *Orientation to the development* cluster and includes such indicators-indicators as: the ability

to determine the areas of development of subordinates, the ability to provide constructive feedback.

The first of these competencies (*Result orientation*) can be attributed to professional competencies, the second (*Willingness to give feedback*) - to managerial ones. Both of them characterize the orientation of the individual to the future, the orientation towards changing oneself and one's competencies.

2. The interrelation of the dynamic aspect of competencies and types of motivation of the personnel of enterprises is revealed.

To obtain this result, the tools of V.I. Gerchikov [2, 3]. The choice of this technique is due to its orientation. The model embedded in it is specially designed for solving managerial problems. It allows you to identify two main types of motivation of employees of the enterprise that determine their activities - achievement motivation and avoidance motivation. In this sense, the technique of V.I. Gerchikov is relevant to the task set in the study to identify, based on the results of comparison, the relationship between the dynamic aspect of the level of competencies and the types of respondents' motivation [4]. To compare the differences between the groups of respondents with high and low scores for each type of motivation, a statistical analysis was carried out and the Mann-Whitney test was used [1]. The analysis revealed the following.

1. Respondents with high scores on four types of motivation (*Professional, Instrumental, Avoidant, and Owner*) have high levels of competencies.

2. Statistically significant differences were obtained in respondents with the *Avoidant* type of motivation. They were identified between respondents with high and low levels for the following competencies:

1) *The ability to prioritize tasks* (the ability to prioritize tasks based on clear criteria for urgency and importance / degree of impact on the result);

2) *Decision-making ability* (ability to make decisions that change the situation, willingness to take responsibility for decisions);

3) *The ability to ensure the understanding of the task by subordinates* (the desire to track the reaction of the subordinate, take feedback from him on understanding the task, check understanding);

4) *Ability to exercise control* (ability to exercise, intermediate and effective control; possession of control tools);

5) *The ability to coordinate the actions of subordinates* (the ability to distribute responsibilities between subordinates according to their abilities);

6) *Efficient use of time* (the desire to keep track of time and fit into a plan).

As a hypothesis, it can be assumed that when the *Avoidant* type of motivation is manifested, the respondents have a reduced desire to take the initiative, actively engage in the implementation of projects and organize the work of other people. It is likely that the manifestation of this type of motivation is expressed in the reduc-

tion of responsibility and the desire to minimize efforts. To reduce the level of the *Avoidant* type of motivation, it is advisable to reorient the training programs and advanced training of managers to the identified areas of competencies development.

Conclusion

The study conducted by the authors showed the growth of managerial and professional competencies of middle and top managers of one of the enterprises in the construction industry after training and development activities. Accounting for the dynamic aspect of the development of managerial and professional competencies made it possible to identify statistically significant differences between the samples of respondents. Based on the results of the analysis of the relationship between the level of competencies and types of motivation, possible directions for professional retraining of personnel were identified.

Acknowledgements.

The study was funded by the Russian Foundation of Basic Research, grant № 19-29-07168mk.

REFERENCES

1. Sidorenko E.V. *Methods of mathematical processing in psychology*. – SPb.: LLC "Speech", 2003. – 350 P.
2. Gerchikov V.I. *Typological concept of labor motivation (part 1)*. // *Motivation and pay*, 2005. № 2. P.53-62 [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://grebennikon.ru/article-wvgs.html>.
3. Bolotova E. *Motivational typology of V. Gerchikov: experience of use* // *Handbook of personnel management*, 2015. № 3 [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://www.axima-consult.ru/motivaciyabolotova.html>.
4. Rozhkov E.M. *Motivation for achieving success and avoiding failures in the work of domestic and foreign scientists* // *Modern Science*. 2014. № 3 [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/motivatsiya-dostizheniya-uspeha-i-izbeganiya-neudach-v-rabotah-otchestvennyh-i-zarubezhnyh-uchenyh> (appeal date: 19.04.2022).